

PREPARATION AND STORAGE OF WELDING CUTTINGS.

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Annotation: *In order to grow new varieties and hybrids that are nutritious for the mulberry silkworm, fertile and resistant to various diseases, it is appropriate to plant mulberry trees on farms by vegetative propagation of mulberry trees. Because when propagated by this method, firstly, the characteristics of the mother tree with vegetative organs of mulberry seedlings grown in this way are preserved, and it is proven that the period of use of secondly established mulberry trees for silkworms is reduced by 2-3 years.*

Key words: *mulberry silkworm, mulberry, seedling, branch, variety, hybrid, nutritious, cutting, graft, productivity, growing season..*

INTRODUCTION. In accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures for more effective use of the existing opportunities in the cocoon industry in the Republic" No. PQ-3910 of August 20, 2018, tasks such as the development of the cocoon industry in the Republic, the construction of fences based on intensive technology, and the implementation of the cocoon industry specified for enterprises.

Despite the fact that Uzbekistan occupies a significant place in the world in terms of cocoon cultivation, the productive mulberry area is only 5-10% of the total mulberry area. It has been achieved through grafting and cultivation of hybrid seedlings over the years.

Today, the step-by-step restoration of existing mulberry groves, increasing the planting of mulberry seedlings on the borders of farm fields, and effective use of existing opportunities will serve to a certain extent in the more intensive continuation of activities aimed at ensuring the employment of the population.

In order to breed productive mulberry trees, any silk agronomist needs to know the structure of mulberry tree organs, mulberry's response to external environmental factors, agrotechnical rules of breeding methods, and methods of feeding silkworms with mulberry leaves. Therefore, it is advisable to use methods that are much cheaper in terms of agrotechnical to reproduce a fruitful mulberry tree.

In addition, in addition to the fact that agrotechnical measures are of great importance in increasing the yield of mulberry, this indicator largely depends on the reproductive characteristics of the plant variety or type.

In order to grow new varieties and hybrids that are nutritious for the mulberry silkworm, fertile and resistant to various diseases, it is appropriate to plant mulberry trees on farms by vegetative propagation of mulberry trees. Because when propagated by this method, firstly, the characteristics of the mother tree with vegetative organs of mulberry seedlings grown in this way are preserved, and it is proven that the period of use of secondly established mulberry trees for silkworms is reduced by 2-3 years.

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Improving the cultivation of fertile mulberry cuttings and seedlings by selecting healthy disease-resistant parent farms and grafting them, improving the food source of cocoons in terms of quantity and quality, saving irrigated land and water in order to increase its economic efficiency, and increasing the economic efficiency of cocoons in the republic. -gradual transition to organization on the basis of mulberry plantation is required..

RESEARCH RESULTS. Scientific researches were carried out in farms of Qalandar ota Ismatillaev, Fergana region, specialized in growing mulberry seedlings, Beshariq Agrotexservis region, specialized in sericulture, in the scientific research institute of sericulture, and in the educational experimental farm of ToshDAU and in the department of sericulture and mulberry production. Before conducting the experiments, the following conditions were created.:

1. The land area is selected.
2. Cuttings of fruitful mulberry trees were prepared.
3. The number of tall mulberry trees on the farm was determined.
4. The number of row-planted mulberry trees on the farm was found.
5. The number of bushes on the farm was determined.
6. Equipment needed for determining the amount of leaves has been prepared..
7. Farmed silkworm hybrids were identified.
8. The equipment used to determine the yield of mulberry leaves was prepared.
9. Electronic and simple scales and their stones for determining the weight of a mulberry leaf.

The main objects in carrying out research.

1. Fruiting mulberry trees and cuttings.
2. Farms.

3. Fruitful mulberry trees.
4. Seedlings.
5. Pens.
6. Roots.
7. Buds.
8. Soil.
9. Open fields.

Research methodology. Cuttings of productive "Oshima", "Tajikistan seedless mulberry", "Jarariq 7", "Hasaki" (comparative), "Pioner" mulberry varieties were used for research. Depending on the research work, the following options were created..

1. Option 1 - Bud grafting technique.
2. Option 2 - Subcutaneous grafting technique.
3. Option 3 - Hasaki tut (comparative).

During the experiment, each option consisted of 2 repetitions, and in bud grafting, 100 grafts were taken each, and a total of 400 grafts were grafted. In subcutaneous grafting, 100 grafts were taken each, and a total of 400 grafts were grafted. Germination and growth of the grafted grafts were measured, and budding periods were determined.

Based on the results of the analysis, the average indicators of grafted grafts were calculated for each hybrid mulberry (presented in Table 1)

Table 1
The number of planted seedlings and sprouted grafts.

It was implemented in April 2021 of the Agrotexservis area of Beshariq district.

Methods of welding	The number of grafts planted			The average length of a one-year branch, cm
	Total pcs	He was bruised from that		
		piece	%	
Tajikistan seedless, mulberry bud graft to do	400	335	83,7	95-105
Incision -7, grafting under the bark of the mulberry variety.	400	350	87,5	100-110

Oshima, mulberry grafting under the bark.	400	320	80	80-90
control Hasaki mulberry variety	400	270	67,5	65-70

100 grafts were taken from Tajik seedless mulberry variety, and a total of 400 buds were grafted onto two-year-old hybrid grafts, of which 335 sprouted and the percentage of germination was 83.7%. During the one-year vegetation period, the average length of the variety is 95-105 cm. Jarariq-7, mulberry variety, 100 grafts were taken, and a total of 400 grafts were grafted under the bark of a two-year-old hybrid graft, of which 350 grafted, the percentage of grafting was 87.5%. During the one-year vegetation period, the average length of the variety is 100-110 cm. 100 grafts were taken from the pioneer mulberry variety, and a total of 400 buds were grafted onto two-year-old hybrid grafts, of which 300 sprouted, the percentage of sprouting was 75%. During the one-year vegetation period, the average length of the variety is 80-85 cm. 100 grafts were taken from Oshima mulberry variety, and a total of 400 grafts were grafted under the bark of a two-year hybrid graft, of which 320 grafts turned blue, the percentage of greening was 80%. During the one-year vegetation period, the average length of the variety is 80-90 cm. Comparative (control) Hasaki mulberry variety was grafted from 100 pieces, and a total of 400 pieces were grafted under the bark of a two-year-old hybrid graft. During the one-year vegetation period, the average length of the variety is 65-70 cm. Based on the experience below, it has been scientifically proven that Jarariq-7 and Tajik seedless mulberry varieties have high performance in all aspects and are different from other varieties, so it is recommended to introduce these varieties into production..

Preparation and storage of pens for welding

Cuttings are made from fertile mulberry trees or branches of one-year fertile mulberry saplings in autumn, winter and early spring (before the aphid movement begins on the tree). For grafting, one-year-old ripe branches of the plant are cut to a length of 40-50 cm, tied in 50-100 pieces and stored in a freezer or special cellars.

So that the temperature of the cellar does not rise excessively, ice is laid on it with a thickness of 1 m and straw is placed on top of it. Then the bundles of sticks are placed on the straw in an upright position and surrounded by straw. If there is no ice, 1 m thick moistened sand is laid. In the next case, the bundles of pencils are placed on top of the sand in two-three layers, between them 8-10 cm and on top of them 30-40 cm thick sand is laid. The temperature of the room where the pen is stored should be

+2-5 degrees and the relative humidity of the air should be 70-80%. If the temperature is higher than this, the cuttings may rot, and if the humidity increases, the cuttings may rot, such cuttings are not suitable for grafting.

The SCIENTIFIC Research Institute of Silk Industry recommends using freezers equipped with an air compressor for storing pens. O'. Kochkorov, a bundle of pencils is wrapped around a bunch of pencils with wet shavings, wrapped with a polyethylene film or moisture-proof paper and placed in a freezer, where its temperature is kept at 2-4 degrees. Under these conditions, the cuttings prepared in late autumn (end of November) can be stored for up to 8-9 months, and the cuttings made in early spring (February-March) before the beginning of aphid movement are well stored until the end of June. Seedlings grafted from these cuttings can turn green up to 90%.

A grafted plant. One- and two-year-old hybrid seedlings, selected according to parentage characteristics, are used as grafts. Pen grafting is done in the middle of March in the southern regions, in April in the regions with average climate, and in the northern regions from the end of April to the beginning of May. If the bud on the cuttings has not grown or dried up, it is possible to graft even until the middle of May.

Before grafting, the part of the seedling close to the root neck is opened and cut at an angle of 35° from one side of the root neck. At the same time, a pen with 2 buds is made from the pen. First, the upper part of the upper bud is cut obliquely, then, taking the pen to the left side, it is obliquely cut 2-3 mm below the lower bud, 2-2.5 cm long. Then the green skin on the opposite side of the cut is scraped off with a knife. The graft is the plant to which it is attached.

In the welding method, due to the cutting of the weld and the weld, they are injured. When they join (join) each other, first of all, the injured tissues are formed on the surface of the cut place. These occur due to longitudinal cutting of xylem (wood) and phloem (bark) tissues. The weld and the weld start to fill using the resulting tissues when they are cut flat and carefully compacted. These tissues are called intermediate tissues. The dead tissue formed due to the cutting of the tissues between the graft and the graft prevents them from bonding. The dead tissue oxidizes and turns yellowish brown under the influence of chlorogenic acid. This thin layer can be lost in two ways: it can be squeezed out due to the development of tissue growth, or it can be completely or partially absorbed by the growing tissue. Finally, the last process in grafting is the formation of nutrient-transmitting canals and their merging with each other due to the action of the cambium tissue. 3.1.1. the cuttings in the picture are taken from the cuttings of a high leaf yielding mulberry tree from the experimental farm of the Jararik Mulberry Research Institute of the Silk Industry Scientific Research Institute, the cuttings are grafted in order to propagate mulberry from vegetative cuttings by grafting, grafting, cloning, and rejuvenating local mulberry trees by grafting and growing productive mulberry seedlings.

It was obtained from the Scientific Research Institute of Sericulture of Uzbekistan
(Fig. 1).

The process of making a cuttings.

samples of cuttings, after planting or grafting of cuttings, its parameters are determined, germination of the grafted area, bluishness, germination of the first axillary bud, appearance of leaves, and the average length of the variety during one year of vegetation is measured.

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